

The Development Of Quality Schools Based On Local Wisdom In Ternate North Maluku

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Abstract: This study aims to determine the development of quality schools based on value of local wisdom in Ternate of North Maluku province. This research is a qualitative multi case study approach in Public Senior High School 1, Public Senior High School 4, Public Senior High School 8, and Islamic Senior High School in Ternate city, qualified according to the size of the city of Ternate of North Maluku province in particular and in general. The research data were collected through observation, interview and documentation techniques. Data were analyzed using qualitative analysis techniques on going interactively. The result was found that to become a quality schools especially in Ternate City, the value of local wisdom such as "Joguru" and "Sangadji" should be the main reference.

Keywords: Development, quality schools, local wisdom values

1 INTRODUCTION

School as the main institution plays a very important role in changing the education system. The success of a school to be qualified also depends on the school to uphold the values of local wisdom. The government through the Ministry of National Education issued a regulation on the principal standard as stipulated in ministerial regulation No. 13/2007 which confirms that a principal should have five dimensions of minimal competences, that is personality, managerial, entrepreneurial, supervision, and social. Based on the five dimensions is expected that principals are able to raise the work spirit of school residents in carrying out their duties, especially the teachers. With the high morale of the work will have an impact on the spirit of student learning that will ultimately produce a generation that ready to compete, capable of competing against an ever changing future. In other words, the Succeed or not of the school to achieve its objectives will be determined by the success of the principal in designing the school organization and upholding the values of local wisdom. That is why in managing the school required a detailed plan, so that there is no overlapping implementation, lack of coordination, less interactive communication, less motivation, not transparent, less thorough, and less understood. Increasing demands on the quality of public schools today, it also increases the demand for overall school performance as a system. All of the school community are expected to perform their basic duties and functions well, and uphold the values of local wisdom applicable in the area. That way, the entire school community has full responsibility for developing all the resources in the school. The effectiveness of school citizen role depends on the ability to cooperate among the citizens of the school, as well as the ability of school residents to control the management of schools to create the learning process. All the school community in carrying out their duties need to have the principles of leadership. Leadership principles include constructive, creative, participative, cooperative, delegative, integrative, rational and objective.

With no concentration of school authority in the hands of the principal because the school implements a collective collegial leadership system, then the entire school community, especially teachers and principals should become a figure, even as a manager who becomes the determinant of school success. Therefore, all people in school must have a good understanding of the vision, mission and the ability to analyze its work. The analysis should be the basis for the implementation of the work. Analytical capabilities is the ability to recognize the advantages and disadvantages of all people in school including the citizens of the school, as well as the potential and opportunities that can be developed, as well as the ability to recognize possible threats. The sharper the analytical power of the school community, are increasingly allowing for achievement. The school principal is one component of education plays an important role in developing more quality schools, this is because there is a relationship between successes in improving the quality of education with quality principal. Quality schools are schools led by principals who certainly qualified. Principal in organizing tasks and functions should have a vision and mission, as well as education management strategy intact and oriented towards quality. This strategy is a systematic and coordinated effort to continuously improve the quality of service, so that the focus is directed to the customer, students, parents, users of graduates, teachers, employees, governments and society. The school principal is the principal desired a strong character, which is not ambivalent and did not hesitate to justify right and wrong to blame. Each school community certainly have a framework of ideas in him which is used to evaluate the information and new experiences. (Carrell Scott & Hoekstra Mark, 2014, pp.1-4) says, knowledge is information for someone as a basis to take action in situations of change, so that the individual or organization able to act in a different way and more effectively. Through knowledge and information, a person is expected to produce the appropriate action and articulate the actions that are most likely, by selecting and assessing the various alternative actions and how those actions should be implemented to fit the desired results or performance. (Carpenter & Murray, 2013, pp.1-3), said there are two types of knowledge that need to be understood by a leader, including the principal, the explicit knowledge and implicit knowledge. First, the explicit knowledge, ie knowledge that can be articulated in formal language including grammatical statements (words and numbers), mathematical expressions, specifications, manuals, and so forth. Second, implicit knowledge, is the personal knowledge that has been

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embedded in individual experience and involves intangible factors such as personal belief, perspective, and value systems. Implicit knowledge is difficult, but not impossible to be articulated into formal language, because the unbiased insight subjective, intuitive, and foreboding. The progress of a nation is determined by the quality of education, because it is through education (schools) can be born human being high quality and competitiveness as one of the development process input row. Without quality schools led by principals of quality, it is impossible goal the building of a nation or region can be realized. Quality education and quality development are like two sides of a coin that can not be separated. The importance of quality education is a growing realization, for the creation of human qualities and the quality of an advanced society and independent can be realized only if public education successfully upgraded. However, the quality of schools and the quality of human resources in Ternate still arguably behind compared with other regions in Indonesia, especially when compared with developed countries. Until now, the low quality of schools and the quality of principals is still a major problem in the development and competitiveness of Ternate city. In fact, the acceleration of globalization and the increasing openness of the free market, Ternate is also faced with competition increasingly broad and tight. There are several studies that are relevant to the title of this article: first, research conducted by David Gurr (2015) with the title "A model of successful school leadership from the international successful school principalship project", which concluded that the context of school education could be changed due to the the role of school leadership, it should be jointly implemented either by the principal, teachers, and students (the school community). The principle is the principal can not run their own schools, but must need other people. (David Gurr, 2015, pp.136-146). Second, the research conducted at the Faculty of the Graduate School at the University of Missouri - Columbia by Gregory W. Mees (2008) with the title "The Relationships Among Principal Leadership, School Culture, And Student Achievement In Missouri Middle Schools", concluded that with increasing pressure from local and central government to improve student achievement, then the problem is more important is an understanding of the moral and ethical obligation to support the academic success, the school principal is now better equipped than ever with insights on how to influence student achievement. The role of the principal, such as: a) the headmaster is key in shaping the culture of the school; b) principals should be able to establish a relationship with the group, internal and external school, such as (1) supervisors and managers of education centers, (2) the school board, (3) peers, (4) parents, (5) surrounding communities, (6) teachers, (7) students, and (8) external groups such as professors, consultants, accreditation bodies, and so on. Effective school principals need to believe in themselves and capable of synergizing perceptions, expectations, and the ability of various groups can provide support to the progress of the school. (Gregory Mees, 2008, pp.1-40). Third, research conducted by Mason Oghenejobo (2009) that emphasize more the style of leadership of the principal, with the title "Personal leadership poverty: A biblical concept for developing transformative leaders", which concluded that the application of particular leadership style of the principal influence on the performance of teachers and the staff, which of course also affect the improvement of student achievement. Leadership style on quality school principals have the same characteristics

as the typology of the value-based juggler, are able to affect all components of the school in the process of school improvement with still oriented on students' progress. The school principal with style, communicate the personal vision and the vision of the school to parents, communities and governments. The school principal has the value of leadership that became the foundation of thinking and acting, which is (a) discipline and work serve as worship, (b) be democratic, (c) be responsible, (d) dare to innovate and confident on the renewal and (e) honest, trustful and open. The school principal also has a well establishment social relationships with the school community, among others; (1) welfare, (2) exemplary, (3) appreciate the achievements of teachers and students, and (4) family, care and welfare. (Mason Oghenejobo, 2009, pp.1-9). Reality shows in the city of Ternate principals not perform its role both in the development of quality schools. Evidently, many schools do not have a planning system that is focused cooperation among teachers is low, management is not optimal school environment is mainly a matter of discipline and cleanliness. (Mulford Bill, 2003, pp.16-18) says an educational institution that is not optimal to run his leadership role will be a strong influence on the creation, formation, and the existence of educational culture, because the culture of the representation of a school principal. School principals are appointed yet furnished and equipped with skills and managerial competencies are adequate, but still believe in the fulfillment of the elements of seniority or rank and class, and also greatly influenced by the subjectivity of the ruler. Educational quality is highly dependent on understanding the principal along with the entire school community for innovation and improvisation in school issues related to curriculum, teaching, managerial, and others that grew out of the activity, creativity, and professionalism possessed. This condition inspires researchers to conduct research on the role of the principal in the development of quality schools based on local wisdom, especially high schools in Ternate City of North Maluku province.

2 METHODOLOGY OF RESEARCH

This research includes qualitative research study approach multi case which examines the role of the principal in the development of quality schools at Senior High School 1, Senior High School 4, Senior High School 8, and Islamic Senior High School in the city of Ternate, which is a quality school according to the size of the city of Ternate of North Maluku Province in general.

2.1. Procedures, Instruments, and Data Collection

This research data collection is done through observation, interviews, and documentation for capturing information about the role of the principal in the development of quality schools, and other factors that influence the working climate of the school. With this technique will obtain the main data and additional data. Words and actions in leading and managing the school from the principal, as well as statements from teachers, administrative staff, school inspectors, school committees, community around the school, the Department of Education, Institute for Education Quality Assurance (LPMP), which is the main data in this research. Instead document school activities is an additional data. The main data and additional data is sourced from the principal activity in leading schools, teachers, administrative staff, supervisors and school committee in carrying out its duties and responsibilities of

each. To obtain accurate data, researchers use focused observation techniques, interviewing techniques, and technical documentation. In the third use of such techniques, the position of the researcher is also a key instrument.

1. Observation Techniques

Observations of this study conducted by the researchers to collect data from the objects of study are recorded from field notes, and then reduced in an observation sheet that has been prepared as a research instrument. In these observations, the researchers also recorded / recorded either by means of unstructured and semi- structured (eg, by asking a number of questions that really wants to be known by researchers) about the activities at the sites. Besides, the researcher can be involved in roles that range from a non-participant to participant intact, such as researchers have ever given the opportunity to have a meeting with the council of teachers at Senior High School 4 Ternate.

2. Interview Techniques

In this technique, the researchers conducted face to face interviews (interviews face to face) with the informants. Interviews addressed to the principals, school inspectors, head of the National Education Office of Ternate, and the Institute for Education Quality Assurance (LPMP) of North Maluku to know in depth the role of the principal in developing quality schools. Instruments interview arranged include questions covering the functions of the principal as a leader in school, education leaders, and efforts to achieve the success of the school to be qualified which include the performance of principals in creating a comfortable working atmosphere, enhancing the quality of learning, to form a good working team, as well as improve student achievement that will encourage the development of schools into quality and high quality.

3. Technical Documentation

During the study, the researchers collected the necessary documents. That is why this research is directed to record the school administration and the policies resulting from the principal's leadership. Administration of the principal is more emphasis on the role of the principal as educational leaders in school. While the data are documented more focused on data that indicate an increased performance of school principals in developing a certain quality.

2.2 Technique of Data Analysis

Analysis of the data in this study using modeling techniques Creswell, because it is considered the most complete and up to date on a variety of data analysis techniques used in research today. There are six (6) steps of data analysis used to illustrate linear and hierarchical built from the ground up, but in this study, researchers looked at more interactive approach; meaning that the various stages are interconnected and not always in accordance with the arrangement.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The principal's role in developing quality school (Senior High School) in Ternate related to the performance of teachers and staff. The quality of school leadership affect the response of teachers to work. The role of the school is the ability to influence people in schools toward achievement of goals. Head good school can be seen from the performance shown

in the managerial aspects owned. School principals as leaders have a high responsibility and full directly in building commitment and cooperation with all the components in the school in the development of quality schools. The school principal as a leader, must implement a number of roles, among others; role as Joguru, Sangadji, stimulus, exemplary, transformative leader, motivator, and role as a supervisor, all of which are intended to develop into a quality school. The school principal should have the potential to create a vision and translate that into a mission and role as a central force in moving the school life. It also understands the duties and functions in developing the overall quality of education.

Joguru

The word "Joguru" according to the language come from almost all regional languages in North Maluku, both in language Ternate, Tidore, Makian, Galela, Tobelo, and others. The word "Joguru" consists of two syllables, "Jou and Teacher", "Jou means' Sir, Sultan, while the" Master "means the Master teacher, Grand Master". So "Joguru" means "Master teacher, one has advantages like the trustees, or people who have tremendous advantages that can be taught to others, people can reduce science for others. In education, Joguru is the principal with a number of advantages that did not exist in others. In kekepalasekolahannya plays, the principal is the person who has the ultimate authority in the school and in the community. That is, Joguru it is a figure that has almost no blemish in him, enviable its behavior, he said, upbringing, education in the family, anything that is attached to him. The duty of whether his or someone else who knows that the person concerned is a definite Joguru followed and carried out all his instructions. The role of the principal as "Joguru" in the development of quality schools for this can not be separated from other roles. Because the role is influenced by social circumstances from both inside and outside and are stable, because the school is an institution that is both complex and unique, then the principal under certain conditions should also have uniqueness. Is complex because the school as an organization in which there are various dimensions to each other interrelated and mutually determine. Being the unique nature, pointing out that the school as an organization has certain characteristics not shared by other organizations. Joguru is a set of behavior expected by others against someone suitable position within a system. Position as Joguru shows the principal is the supreme leader and to be in charge, nurturing, and protecting all human resources in the school. In this role, the principal is responsible for the highest good of the overall implementation of the educational process at school, and used as a reference in society at large. As a Joguru, fair if the principal is required to seek the implementation of the educational process effectively and efficiently, including resolving issues other civic life. The school principal is the post of leader also must obtain legitimacy from the people, the position could not be filled by people without being based on considerations, because not all principals capable of bearing the title as Joguru. That is, anyone who will be appointed head of the school should be determined through procedures and certain requirements, not only as: educational background, experience, age, rank, and integrity, as long as this happens, but should also take into consideration also the background behind family, community legitimacy, adherence to religious teachings, as well as attitudes and daily behavior obtained based on feedback from

the community. Joguru in his leadership role as it will greatly affect even the school will determine the development of a certain quality. Indicators of the role of the principal as Joguru is to set an example or role model who looks at discipline in dressing, maintaining personal hygiene, always fulfilling the obligation to worship the Lord, attendance at school, on time, how to use the time in school, how to communicate politely and appreciate everyone, his family life to be a reference, its influence in the community is very large, can hold his speech, when speaking, only important and useful are delivered, humorous but not excessive, laughing but not laughing, always hold the principle, and understated but very firm, primarily related to the rule.

Sangadji

The word "Sangadji" by language, a language derived from some areas in North Maluku (Ternate, Tidore, Makian, Gamkonora, Bacan, and Galela) which means the head of government/ Sultan. Thus the leader in any institution including educational institutions called "Sangadji". In practice, Sangadji has two vice-called "Bobato" namely; Bobato world and the hereafter. The word "Bobato" themselves by language, also for of some of the local language which means "servant". So "Bobato world" means the chairman of the maid who was in charge of the problems of life in the world or Umaraa. While "Bobato hereafter" means the head assistant in charge of issues related to life in the hereafter or the clergy. Sangadji power is very strong and entrenched. Sangadji is a leader with the charisma that high. At first, only practiced in government or empire. In the world of education or school, Sangadji position is the principal, and the Bobato as the vice principal, of course with the duties and roles of each determined by Sangadji, and should be announced by Sangadji itself through a general meeting. The role of the principal as Sangadji in the development of quality schools is a way or business principals in influencing, encouraging, guiding, directing, moving, even occasionally need to force all people in schools and other relevant parties to work or participate in achieving the objectives of the school that has set. This looks at all the schools studied, that principal as a Sangadji certainly have the skills or abilities more than the other principals that have not been considered as Sangadji, such as the ability to see things that are not seen with the eyes, the ability to feel something which is not seen, the ability to read the minds of others, good communication skills, have the technical ability in the field, has a sharp analytical ability, be firm and bold decision-making, high work ethic and have a clear vision. People who hold power are also called Sangadji whose power is very strong and is central in determining school policy. The school principal who has the title as Sangadji only those who have excess remarkable that does not exist in others, they were able to see something that can not be dilhat by others, could hear were not heard by others, even can control natural phenomena though , actually have a sixth sense. The role of the principal as Sangadji can be said that all school policies set by principals via a joint meeting with the teachers, and at that meeting, whether or not there are proposals from members of the meeting there is no problem, subordinate stay implement. All orders, administration and division of tasks well done, even without any consultation with the principal. The subordinates are also sometimes limit the relationship with the principal, except in formal situations, all tasks assigned run professionally. Although, all citizens of the

relationship of the school with the school head is always full of intimacy, familiarity and suave. The role of the principal as this Sangadji more bases itself on power and coercion are always to be obeyed, because that's the concept of leadership Sangadji. The role of the principal as Sangadji sometimes just giving orders, rules, and restrictions. All teachers and staff certainly submit and obey implement without much question. They viewed the principal as a Sangadji with a number of advantages attached to it, also because they are already accustomed to be faithful to the command. The key is the principal must act as Sangadji, aim only want to make the school better quality. In this connection other than as supreme leader at the school, the principal must also be community leaders, principals also be role models in society. Sangadji role as synonymous with authoritarian leadership, but a Sangadji still want to open themselves to receive suggestions and feedback, even criticisms for improvement agencies, only the community keeping a distance with the principal. It is caused by Sangadji status of the school principal. These conditions provide opportunities for principals to develop the role of the school to be more qualified, mangingat rarely any internal barriers in carrying out duties as principal. Simply put, the role of the principal as Sangadji as follows:

- a. Authority and the authority of principals and vice-principals and even the very large.
- b. The subordinates are always ready to be given the command to work, and almost no protest.
- c. The subordinate position the head of the school is very high and difficult to reach.
- d. Subordinate always keep a distance with the principal.
- e. Decisions and policies are always made by the principal, because the style of leadership that is always central, but still open to receive suggestions and feedback and even criticism.
- f. Supervision is done strictly on monitoring the principal by using the principles of participation, but oversight is assessing.
- g. The initiative came from the leader of that style of principals felt more and feel fully responsible for the school's progress.
- h. There is an opportunity to give advice, principals feel the most correct but realized as a common man.
- i. Sometimes a little stiff in attitude that is not always the situation and conditions but a little pushy.
- j. The application of punishment to subordinates is always carried out, both oral and written, of course according to the degree of error made.

The results of this study also indicate that quality schools the dream and hope of everyone, including people in Ternate City and North Maluku in general. The studied schools have fulfilled that expectation, although still need further coaching. That is why all school community, especially teachers and principals, must be at the forefront to provide guidance, direction, motivation, and even command to maintain and improve school quality. In everyday behavior, all school community must uphold the values of local wisdom as well as to set an example, but without being perceived by subordinates, he also sometimes did not realize that all the actions are intended to develop the school into quality. That is why all the actions of the school community, especially teachers and principals during the school should always be in accordance with what he said. Some teachers encountered

during the study said that when applying these two local values of wisdom in the development of quality schools, the teachers and principals seemed to be very high not only when they were in school but also in the community. The principal with the teacher is always the first to start any program at school. The study also found that the principal did not boast of himself that he was the principal. Principals always build good communication with anyone in school. Some teachers acknowledge that the inspirational figure and the driving force of change that his promises, which his words can always hold, can be followed in school or out of school. The principal is always principled at which point he should stand in front to set an example, at which point to stand in the middle to provide motivation, and at which point should be behind to be a driver. All this he did with the hope of being an example or role model for all school community, especially in developing quality school.

4 CONCLUSIONS

One factor that is often highlighted by many parties about the role of the principal in the development of the school to be qualified, especially in the city of Ternate is the professionalism of principals and teachers in their duties. This is reasonable because the quality of education of a region depends on the quality of teachers, and the quality of teachers is determined by the desire of teachers themselves in improving the quality which is supported by the ability of qualified principals, as well as local government policy is clear and unequivocal. School quality is determined by the quality of the teacher's principal, not the amount of funds for education and great facilities. If the teacher is good quality and is led by the head of the school is good then it will be ascertained school quality school. Principals who already qualified is not enough, if you apply the leadership style that does not fit with the characteristics and style of thinking people in the area. Contribution of education to regional progress and the nation is certainly not merely the provision of education, but quality education, quality education resulting from quality schools both in terms of inputs, processes, outputs, and outcomes. Input quality education is the teachers who are also qualified, led by the principals of quality, student quality, quality facilities, and various aspects of quality education as well. The process of quality education is a learning process quality. Output quality education are graduates who have the requisite competence. While quality education outcomes are graduates who are able to continue to pursue higher education or absorbed in the world of business or industry. The role played by each school principal to develop quality school appropriate study's findings are, a) Each school principal must act as "Joguru" in the development of quality schools, b) The principal must act as "Sangadji" in the development of quality schools, c) the principal must act as a driving force in the development of quality schools, d) the principal must act as a highly capable model in the development of quality schools, e) the principal must act as a transformational leader in the development of quality schools, f) the principal must act as motivator in the development of quality schools, and g) the principal must also act as watchdogs in developing quality schools.

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